

SUPPORTER

**Roadmap towards the
development of a 4I-GEP,
Charles University,
Faculty of Physical
Education and Sport (CU)**

The first version of the CU roadmap

This document is the first version of Charles University, Faculty of Physical Education and Sport (CU) to develop an inclusive, innovative, intersectional and impactful gender equality plan (4I-GEP). It has been developed within the context of their participation in the SUPPORTER project by the CU team, with the support of SUPPORTER's expert partners. The full text, as well as other partners' roadmaps, are to be found in SUPPORTER's deliverable: [D4.1 Report on the design of the institutional roadmaps.](#)

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Introduction

The SUPPORTER project aims to foster gender-related, **sustainable**, and **transformative** institutional changes in sports higher education institutions paying specific attention to the challenge of **gender-based violence and leading to the development of inclusive, innovative, intersectional and impactful gender equality plans (4I-GEPs)**.

The transformation of existing institutional GEPs into 4I-GEPs is achieved through the co-design and implementation of individual roadmaps, tailored to the needs of each implementing organisation.

This document outlines the development and implementation of the roadmap of Charles University (Faculty of Physical Education and Sport) within the SUPPORTER project. **It describes the grounding actions to be taken and the individual steps to be followed.**

The CU roadmap encompasses a set of Grounding Actions (GAs) to be implemented from March 2024 to June 2025. These actions address mandatory and recommended thematic GEP elements ([Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans](#)) under-addressed in the IO's existing institutional GEP. Critical challenges, including engagement and participation barriers in implementing the roadmaps, resource limitations and organisational resistance, have been identified, alongside measures to effectively address them.

This roadmap represents a tailored strategy, responsive to the unique needs and opportunities within CU, structured in a set of Grounding Actions which are going to be carried out within a 16-month implementation period (March 2024 – June 2025). It is crucial to emphasise that, while carefully designed, the roadmap is a living document, likely to undergo several adjustments to effectively address evolving challenges and time constraints and feedback gathered during the organisation of the planned activities. This shall ensure that the roadmap remains relevant and conducive to transformative change through the development, at the end of this period, of the new 4I-GEPs.

Development of institutional roadmaps

A roadmap is a detailed document that sets the steps and actions (a.k.a grounding actions) necessary to achieve institutional changes into a common strategic framework and timeframe and has the key features of being flexible and progressive.

In the context of SUPPORTER, a roadmap provides a clear and detailed plan of grounding actions that will foster the institutional changes needed to pave the way for the development of the 4I-GEP.

After national and institutional mapping and self-assessment of the existing GEP and institutional policies, the CU team co-designed their roadmap with their internal stakeholders and the support of the SUPPORTER mentoring team from December 2023 to March 2024. This participatory approach ensured that the roadmap addressed specific problems in the institution and tailored it to the needs of sports higher education.

Steps

The co-design of the institutional roadmaps consisted of five steps:

1. Launch of the co-design process: The roadmap concept, as well as the scope and objectives of institutional roadmaps, were introduced to CU.
2. Internal consultation process: Meetings were held with different types of internal stakeholders in a consultation process that led to the first draft of the institutional roadmaps
3. Consultation with the mentoring team: CU participated in consultation meetings with the mentoring team, which consisted of consortium experts.
4. Internal review process: CU reviewed the roadmap internally to address any previously identified challenges and gaps.
5. Finalization of the roadmap.

Figure 1 – Steps to co-design partners' roadmaps within SUPPORTER

CU: organisation

Charles University is based in Prague and has a total of 17 faculties, two of which are in two other cities. The university is the oldest one in Central Europe, established in 1348. The Faculty of Physical Education and Sport is one of the youngest faculties established in 1953. The legal representative of Charles University is the Rector, heads of faculties are deans. The rector is elected internally by members of the academic senate of the university rectorate, for four years. The deans are also elected internally by faculty members for four years. Charles University has historically voted its first woman rector two years ago. The Faculty of Physical Education and Sport has had a new dean for one and a half years. The members of the SUPPORTER project consist of vice deans, international relations employees, expert academic employees, PhD students.

Gender equality at CU

Public document

CU GEP has been published on the official website (Czech and English versions) of Charles University in the “Gender Equality” section. It does not include signatures, only a responsible person – in this case Marie Vymazalová - a Member of the Rector’s Board for Social Affairs and Sustainable Development. The publication of this document was communicated by the rectorate through email to all contact persons of all 17 faculties (selected members of the Social Affairs Board from each faculty).

Roadmap towards the development of a 4I-GEP

The context

There is a lack of communication and a scarcity of activities in the area of GBV at the FPES – no regular trainings, no actions for students, no active prevention, no department is fully based in GBV. There is also a capacity problem, as the faculty is understaffed.

Aims and Objectives

The overall aim of implementing the 4I-GEP (Inclusive, Impactful, Innovative, Intersectional Gender Equality Plan) at FPES is to foster a culture of gender equality and inclusivity within the realm of sports education. Through targeted actions and initiatives, a sport-centred approach will be promoted that addresses gender disparities, combats gender-based violence (GBV) including sexual harassment, and embraces inclusiveness, impact, innovation, and intersectionality.

Main Objectives:

a) Adopting a Sport-Centred Approach:

- Integrate gender-sensitive educational modules and research methodologies into specific courses.
- Provide training to researchers on gender-inclusive practices.
- Collaborate with staff from other faculties to summarise courses with GE dimensions and promote the relevant courses to students.

b) Addressing Gender-Based Violence:

- Assess current knowledge of GBV and sexual harassment.
- Raise awareness and educate staff and students.
- Identify and clarify available support services.

c) Considering Inclusiveness, Impact, Innovation, and Intersectionality:

- Promote inclusivity and diversity.
- Clarify internal roles for GEP implementation.
- Drive innovation in gender equality practices.
- Embrace an intersectional approach to gender equality

Structure of the roadmap

Period of implementation Grounding actions/Action lines GEP element

Period of implementation	Grounding actions/Action lines	GEP element
PROJECT PERIOD	GA1 – Raising awareness on gender+ equality and inequalities in sports environments	Training
	GA2 – Forming educational modules and material for staff and students on gender, sexuality and intersectionality	Training Gender dimension in research and teaching
	GA3 – Training activities on how gender impacts sports research	Training Gender dimension in research and teaching
	GA4 – Gathering information on GBV and sexual harassment	Data collection and monitoring Measures against GBV
	GA5 – Awareness-raising on GBV at the institutional level and beyond	Training Measures against GBV
	GA6 – Redefining the contact persons job description for GEP implementation	Dedicated resources Work-life balance and organisational culture Measures against GBV Gender equality in recruitment
4I – GEP IMPLEMENTATION PERIOD	Follow-up survey examining whether the knowledge of GBV in the faculty has improved	Measures against GBV
	Assessment of student/researcher training satisfaction regarding new gender-based	Integrating gender dimensions into research

	initiatives	and teaching content
SUSTAINABILITY PERIOD	Review and development of a new GEP advancing on the achievements which have already been made	All
	Knowledge-sharing events with other faculties and higher education institutions in the Czech Republic	All
	Enlargement of impact by exchanging information with external stakeholders	All

The Grounding Actions

A set of 6 Grounding Actions are envisaged to achieve the purposes of this roadmap and pave the way towards the development of a new, 4I-GEP, which will be sports-specific and place emphasis on addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Each of these dimensions is comprehensively addressed by the different actions comprising the roadmap, as depicted in the following table.

Dimension	GA1	GA2	GA3	GA4	GA5	GA6
<i>Intersectional</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Innovative</i>		x	x		x	x
<i>Inclusive</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Impactful</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Tailored to sports</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x

GA1 – Raising awareness on gender+ equality and inequalities in sports environments

GA1 is focused on raising awareness activities on gender equality and understanding of gender issues, stereotypes and biases in the academic sport environment.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training

b. Objectives

- To get the topic of gender equality on the organisation's/faculty's agenda
- To promote a uniform understanding of the concept of gender+ equality in higher education

- Raise awareness and understanding of gender issues, stereotypes and biases in the sports environment both at institutional and at local/national level.

c. Implementation plan

1. Set up a working team (incl. comms, students and/or staff) and clearly allocate tasks
2. Develop the scheme (Define objectives, target audience, timeframe and budget, activities and desired outcome)
3. Design the material (define appropriate channels, create the visuals)
4. Finalise the material and seek approval (if necessary)
5. Implement the activities (Suggested activities: Workshop/panel discussion events for academic/admin staff and students – e.g. for new students in an induction week, 1 local stakeholder event for external stakeholders, 1 social media campaign)
6. Impact evaluation and suggestion for future relaunch

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, GE expert at Uni/Faculty, students and staff reps

Only consulting: GE/Ethics Committee, mid-level management, external consultants

Only informing: High-level management, external stakeholders

e. Potential obstacles

- Low engagement of participants (lack of time/interest of faculty staff, students and external participants to attend informational sessions, workshops and events).
- Lack of financial resources
- Internal resistances (e.g. the campaign does not get approval)

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Develop a communication campaign scheme	Project team	Communication campaign plan	Human resources	April – May 2024
Design the campaign	Project team Department for multimedia	Campaign material	Multimedia tools Human resources	May – June 2024
Launch the campaign: Organising informational sessions and workshops	Project team	Feedback from participants No. of participants	Communication platforms Multimedia tools and Human resources	June – October 2024
Develop an online platform with GEP-	Project team	Developed platform	Human resources	March-May

related documents	Department for multimedia		Software/technological equipment	2024
Evaluating impact	Project team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms	Human resources	October – November 2024

GA2 – Forming educational modules and material for staff and students on gender, sexuality and intersectionality

Co-operation and co-creation with knowledgeable staff in the areas of gender, sexuality and intersectionality from other faculties to form educational modules for staff and students.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training

Thematic: Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content

b. Objectives

These actions aim to improve the general knowledge of gender, sexuality and intersectionality by enriching existing courses with gender-sensitive topics and encouraging greater participation of students within and beyond the faculty of physical education and sport. Collaboration with academic staff at the university level to create holistic educational materials will address the current knowledge gap and increase teaching standards and curricula. This approach not only aims to improve the academic community's general knowledge of these topics but also to create a supportive environment that encourages exploration and understanding of complex social issues, ultimately contributing to a more inclusive and informed academic setting.

c. Implementation plan

To enhance gender sensitivity in our educational and research practices, we have laid out a focused implementation plan. Our first step involves integrating gender-sensitive elements into the teaching of an existing Research methodology course for doctoral students. The effectiveness of this initiative will be judged by updates to the course syllabus, participation rates of doctoral students, and their feedback. Essential resources for this include expert consultations and training materials for the instructors.

Simultaneously, we will enrich the subjects "Academic Writing" (focused on work with publication activity/results of scientific work) and "Violence, Individual, and Society" courses for undergraduates with gender dimension discussions, managed by Undergraduate Program Coordinators and course instructors. This will necessitate revised course materials and instructor training on gender issues.

FPES will also initiate the co-creation and wide distribution of educational materials, specifically brochures and information leaflets focusing on gender, sexuality, and intersectionality. These materials will be disseminated to both staff and students, extending from the university level down to

our faculty, ensuring a broad reach and impact. This effort aims to provide accessible, foundational knowledge that supports further learning and discussion within our academic community.

To support active learning and engagement, FPES will promote and motivate students to enrol in relevant subjects. This includes courses offered within our faculty and those available in other faculties, covering lectures and seminars on gender, sexuality, and intersectionality. By doing so, we intend to foster a multidisciplinary learning environment that encourages a deeper understanding of these critical issues.

The effectiveness of these actions will be measured a) by updated course syllabi, student enrolment numbers, and course feedback, about updated modules and b) by the number of digital and physical brochures/leaflets distributed throughout the university and faculty levels.

d. Stakeholders involved

Project team, Study department, Academics, Department of Internal Affairs, Department of International Relations, Students, Rectorate (CU Point/Board for Social Affairs and Sustainable Development/Council for Equal Opportunities)

e. Potential obstacles

- Resistant attitudes amongst staff and students. This could be overcome by targeted promotion and education based not only on faculty management but also on key players among students and employees.
- Lack of financial resources for the training of the module instructors

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
Assess training needs of course teachers	Project team GE experts at Uni	Focus group discussion to identify needs	Human resources	April 2024
Training of course teachers	Project team GE experts at Uni External experts	Increased knowledge of course teachers on GE issues	Human resources External expertise Venue	April – May 2024
Review existing material on selected courses	Course teachers Project team	Report on suggested areas for improvement	Human resources	May – June 2024
Revise and enrich course syllabi and material	Course teachers Project team	Consultation process with external experts Revised course material	Human resources External expertise	June – September 2024

Finalise course material and seek approval	Course teachers Upper management	Approved syllabi and course material	Human resources	September 2024
Inform students/staff of new, gender-sensitive course content (e.g. in induction week)	Course teacher Project team Communication team	Increased student enrolment (10-20) Student feedback	Human resources Communication/evaluation tools	September 2024 – January 2025
Compilation and revision of educational material	Project team Internal Affairs	Revised educational material	Human resources (time for revision) Revised educational material Expert consultation	April – May 2024
Distribution of educational material	Internal Affairs Department International Relations Department Rectorate Communication team	Number of digital/physical distribution	Human resources Communication tools	July – August 2024

GA3 – Training activities on how gender impacts sports research

Training for both domestic and international researchers on how gender impacts sports research, e.g. methodologies, sampling, inclusive and intersectional practices.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training

Thematic: Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content

b. Objectives

The purpose of this action is to fill in knowledge gaps and increase awareness of the impact of gender in sports research. Currently, there is no such training for researchers, causing research output and quality to be lesser than other European higher education research institutes. By improving knowledge of gender amongst the research community, gender equality practices can be mainstreamed through the spread of information and education. The goal is to better equip internal stakeholders so that issues relating to gender in academia can be challenged.

c. Implementation plan

We will organise gender-sensitive research practice training for academics and researchers. This starts with defining the training scheme’s objectives, target audience, activities and time plan. After outlining the scheme and individual activities, GE experts will be identified internally and, in case internal resources are not sufficient, external expertise will be sought. The preparation of the training material precedes the launch of the training scheme. After its completion, the training will be evaluated to identify strengths and weaknesses, amendments will be made and the possibility to repeat on a periodical basis will be explored.

We will measure success through the attendance records, and training reports. Required resources include expert facilitators, session venues or platforms, and training content.

Overall, success will be indicated by updated course syllabi, student participation numbers, and comprehensive training feedback. To support these initiatives, we will discuss allocating a budget for expert consultations, and material development, and use communication and evaluation tools to measure impact, aiming to foster a more inclusive academic environment.

d. Stakeholders involved

Project team, Academic employees, Research employees, pre-graduate and postgraduate students, External trainers

e. Potential obstacles

Potential obstacles include student/researcher apathy and a lack of staff to take charge of such training. There could be bigger propagation and motivation for attendance. It is also important to find suitable experts for training.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
Define the training scheme	Project team Study department Internal Affairs Department	Outline of planned training	Human resources	May – June 2024
Seeking internal and external expertise	Project team Internal Affairs Department Communications team	List of trainers	Human resources Financial resources for external trainers	July 2024
Preparation of training material	Project team Trainers IT team (if necessary)	PPT presentation Training material	Human resources; Software and other digital tools	September 2024

Delivery of Training for academic/research staff	Internal Affairs department	Staff participation numbers	Expert facilitator	September – November 2024
	Trainers	Feedback	Communication/evaluation tools	
	Project team			
Impact evaluation	Internal Affairs department	Knowledge increases through knowledge-control pre/post training questionnaire No. of participants Participant feedback	Human resources	December 2024
	Project team		Evaluation tools	

GA4 – Gathering information on GBV and sexual harassment

Collection of data on the current state of knowledge regarding GBV at the faculty level.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Data collection and monitoring.

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment.

b. Objectives

These actions aim to understand what the current state of knowledge is within the faculty regarding GBV and sexual harassment, such as, how people think it happens, what counts as GBV/SH, and what resources they know are available if GBV/SH occurs. It is unclear what services/resources are available to victims, so clarification is required so that they can seek help quickly. These objectives would address the lack of information regarding GBV and SH available to staff and students.

c. Implementation plan

FPES will utilise the results of a university-wide questionnaire that has been previously distributed. This will allow us to leverage existing data on the perceptions and awareness of GBV and sexual harassment across the university. Analysing this data will provide a foundational understanding that can guide further inquiries and actions. The results will also indicate whether any GBV-related data is missing and recommendations for nuancing the existing questionnaire or introducing additional data collection methods will be issued.

Indicators:

Comprehensive analysis of the university questionnaire data, providing a baseline understanding of GBV and sexual harassment awareness.

d. Stakeholders involved

Project team, Study department, Academics, Department of Internal Affairs, Department of International Relations, Students, Rectorate (CU Point/Board for Social Affairs and Sustainable Development/Council for Equal Opportunities)

e. Potential obstacles

- Lack of understanding
- Low engagement (due to limited time, inadequate efforts for the recruitment of participants, and little interest in GBV)
- Lack of financial resources
- Internal resistances (to identify the need or value of a gender audit or to give prominence to latent inequalities)

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
Existing data analysis	Rectorate (Council of Equal Opportunities) Internal Affairs Department	Understanding of GBV and SH's current awareness	Staff time for analysis (from Internal Affairs Dpt) Communication with rectorate – their provision of existing data and their conducted analysis	October 2024
Suggestions for additional data collection	Project team Internal Affairs Department	Report with recommendations	Human resources	November 2024
Suggestions of additional tools for data collection	Project team Internal Affairs Department	Report with recommended data collection methods/tools beyond the questionnaire	Human resources	November 2024

GA5 – Awareness-raising on GBV at the institutional level and beyond

This Grounding Action develops and implements an awareness-raising, evidence-based campaign on Gender-Based Violence in the sports context.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

Based on the results of the knowledge-gathering carried out in the previous GA, awareness-raising initiatives and education will address the presented gaps in order to increase understanding among staff and students regarding the concept and forms of gender-based violence (physical, sexual, psychological, economic and financial, sexual harassment, online) in the sports context. This will assist in creating a safe environment and a culture of respect and equality. Also, staff and students will be introduced to the relevant regulatory framework and internal procedures in place (reporting and case management, support mechanisms) in a simple and comprehensive manner. Beyond the institutional level, an awareness-raising event will be organised to extend a uniform understanding of GBV and to promote a culture of zero tolerance towards gender-based violence within the sports context.

c. Implementation plan

Building on the insights gained from the previous GBV information gathering, we will launch awareness-raising and educational activities designed to address identified knowledge gaps. These initiatives will be tailored to our faculty's context, with a particular emphasis on the intersection of GBV, sexual harassment, and sports. Staff and students will be informed of the plan for GBV awareness raising at the Academic meeting in January 2025.

Support from vice deans (for Internal Affairs and International Relations) will be crucial in disseminating information and fostering an environment that values and promotes gender equality. Their involvement will help amplify the reach and impact of the messages being communicated, ensuring that the importance of the GEP is recognised at all levels of the faculty (Information will be disseminated mainly at international staff meetings, which happen every month, at meetings happening every week for top and middle management, and through newsletters which go to all employees and students).

Vice-deans and contact persons will also be participating in many GE-oriented events, for example: "Women who inspire" (March 8th), participation in the new EqualEdu project, and participation in the LERU-CE7 international workshop "Inclusive GEPs in FPE10" on March 14th and 15th. This could also help with information dissemination and fostering an environment that promotes gender equality.

Also, a local stakeholder event (e.g. in the form of an awareness day) will be organised to raise awareness of targeted external stakeholders such as sports clubs, trainers, associations, umbrella organisations, and public authorities.

Indicators:

Attendance: Attendance records for awareness-raising activities will be meticulously maintained. High participation rates will indicate a strong community interest and commitment to addressing GBV and sexual harassment.

Event Report: After the events or activities, we will compile comprehensive event reports. These reports will document the activities conducted, participation levels, participant feedback, and any measurable outcomes or shifts in awareness and understanding among attendees.

After GA4 and G5, in case of anyone experiencing GBV, firstly there will be an app available for FPES (it is already being prepared), where individuals can report an incident. In the app, there will be a chatting function, where an individual reporting an incident will have the possibility to chat with our contact persons at the faculty. Depending on the situation, the individual will have the option to only chat anonymously with the contact person to find a solution, or in more serious cases they will have the opportunity to decide if they want to come personally and talk about the incident (unanonymizing themselves). Depending on the situation and seriousness, incidents are solved either on the faculty level with contact persons, or they can be pushed to the university level for ombuds persons. Secondly, as there is already an ombudsperson at the university level established and right now 2 contact persons are established at the faculty, where students and employees can report any incident (GBV, sexual harassment etc), there is no need to create another contact point/bureau and incorporate it to our roadmap. For more on our faculty contact point see GA6 (Redefining the contact persons job description for GEP implementation).

d. Stakeholders involved

Faculty management - contributing to plan development and coordination, overseeing execution

Academics – offering expertise on gender-based violence

Rectorate – EOC - Providing institutional support

Internal Affairs - facilitating communication

International Relations Department, Rectorate – Council of Equal Opportunities, Members of the Rector’s Board for Social Affairs and Sustainable Development

e. Potential obstacles

The largest obstacle to this would be securing adequate funds. To prevent this, talks must be held with the relevant managing staff at the rectorate. Currently, it is unclear whether internal staff hold the adequate knowledge to host and produce meaningful, well-informed awareness-raising initiatives. This can be overcome through consultation with external experts and putting out a university-wide call for expertise or using information from other projects' toolkits to reinforce knowledge of key actors. Other obstacles include low engagement (due to lack of time/interest), and internal and external resistances.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
Development of an awareness-raising programme	Project team Internal Affairs department Communications team	Document of the campaign scheme	Human resources	September 2024

Design the material	Project team Internal Affairs Department Communications team	Complete material of the campaign	Software Communication tools Human resources	October – November 2024
Finalise and seek approval	Project team Internal Affairs department Top management	Official approval by the management	Human resources	November 2024
GBV awareness-raising promotion at Academic meeting	Student Body Internal Affairs Department Top management (vice-deans)	Staff and student attendance	Human resources Venue	January 2025
Awareness-raising activities (campaign/workshop)	Project team International Affairs Department	Event report, attendance	Event venue Staff time (International Affairs Dpt) for organisation	January 2025-June 2025
External stakeholder event	Project team International Affairs	Number of participants	Event venue Human resources	February – March 2025
Evaluate the scheme's impact and explore the possibility of future relaunch	Project team International Affairs Department	Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms	Human resources	May – June 2025

GA6 – Redefining the contact persons job description for GEP implementation

This grounding action will expand the existing ombudspersons' responsibilities according to the implementation of the new GEP.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

Thematic: Work-life balance and organisational culture; Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment; Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

b. Objectives

The objective of creating a role dedicated to the execution of these tasks is to maintain accountability. Currently, the faculty is reliant on external advisors/ombuds people. Although this

should remain a top-down approach to addressing gender equality, a bottom-up approach could help improve more sympathetic attitudes to the GEP.

c. Implementation plan

To effectively implement the GEP with redefined internal roles aimed at bridging the gap between top-down approaches and grassroots, empathetic engagement, the following structured steps are proposed:

Defining the Mandate for contact persons:

First, a distinction is made between contact roles: one dedicated to employees and another for students. These roles will serve as primary points of contact for all GEP-related inquiries, suggestions, or concerns, ensuring that stakeholders have a clear and accessible channel for communication.

Allocation of Tasks:

Allocate specific tasks associated with each role. This includes the responsibility for forwarding information to all stakeholders, distributing relevant updates, resources, and opportunities through email, and actively mentioning these points during faculty meetings to keep the community informed and engaged.

Seeking Approval from Upper Management:

Present the proposed redefinition of roles and allocation of tasks to upper management (Dean's Board) for approval. This step is crucial for ensuring that the initiative has the necessary backing and authority to be implemented effectively.

Ongoing Training Appointed Gender Equality Persons:

The contact persons are already continuously provided (monthly) with the necessary training for the individuals appointed to these positions (ombudsperson positions). Training is provided by a university-level ombudsperson and covers the methods for effective communication, strategies for promoting gender equality within the institution, mediation etc.

Redefinition of these internal roles aim to bridge the gap between top-down approaches and the need for more grassroots, empathetic engagement with gender equality initiatives.

To effectively implement these redefined tasks, we will start by distinguishing the contact roles: one dedicated to employees and another for students. These roles will serve as primary points of contact for all GEP-related inquiries, suggestions, or concerns, ensuring that stakeholders have a clear and accessible channel for communication.

The responsibility of forwarding information to affected stakeholders will be a key function of these roles. This will include the distribution of relevant updates, resources, and opportunities via email and the active mention of these points during faculty meetings. This ensures that all members of the faculty are kept informed and engaged with the GEP's progress and initiatives.

Indicators:

Number of Requests/Initiatives: Tracking the number of requests or initiatives received by the contact persons for employees and students will serve as a key indicator of engagement and active participation in the GEP. A higher number of requests or initiatives will indicate a growing interest and involvement in gender equality matters within the faculty.

Engagement Metrics: The effectiveness of information dissemination efforts will be measured through engagement metrics, such as the reach of emails, attendance at meetings where GEP initiatives are discussed, reports from these meetings and the level of participation in related activities.

d. Stakeholders involved

Internal Affairs Department, Contact persons for staff and students, Dean’s Board

e. Potential obstacles

Since it will not be a primary job but a newly added agenda, we can meet with some unwillingness. This could be overcome by giving the person additional pay to their full-time agreement.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
Defining the Mandate for Contact Persons	Project team Internal Affairs Department	Redefined job description	Human resources	March 2024 – May 2024
Allocation of tasks	Dean's Board	Qualitative assessment of the requests/initiatives by the ombudsperson Job description for ombudsperson	Human resources	June – July 2024
Seeking Approval from Upper Management	Dean's Board	New positions approved	Human resources	September 2024
Training of appointed Gender Equality Persons	Project team Internal Affairs Department External trainers	Increased capacity of GE persons	Human resources; Training material; Financial resources for external expertise/training attendance	October – December 2024
Communication of new roles and ways for effective	Internal Affairs department Communications	Information email Meeting with relevant	Human resources	November – December

collaboration with relevant institutional bodies	team	bodies		2024
Support from faculty leaders	Vice-dean for Internal Affairs	The number of emails that reaches	Human resources	January – June 2025
	Vice-dean for International Relations	Meeting attendance and reports Activity participations		

General timeline

